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SURFACE LAYER THICKNESS, DEFECTS AND STRENGTH OF GRAPHITE

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Abstract

The article proposes an empirical formula that determines the thickness of the surface layer $R(I)$ and the length of nanocracks L_{nm} of a solid body. It is applied to graphite, which has an anisotropic structure. It is shown that the thickness of the $R(I)_a$ layer (and the length of nanocracks L_{nm}) varies from 0.9 to 1.24 nm in the upper plane, and the thickness of the $R(I)_c$ layer (and the length of nanocracks L_{nm}) varies from 2.46 to 3.39 nm perpendicular to this plane. The number of layers of graphite is 3-5. This is due to changes in the density of graphite and its layered structure. The mechanical properties differ both in the longitudinal (for example, Young's modulus $E_a \approx 6$ GPa) and in the transverse directions ($E_c \approx 25$ GPa). The Young's modulus of graphite is 10 ÷ 100 times less than that of most metals. Cracks L_{nm} , L_{4nm} , L_c for graphite are caused by their dislocation interaction. The dislocation density is maximum in the $R(I)$ layer $\rho_{nm} = 10^{18} \text{ m}^{-2}$ (in the longitudinal direction), $\rho_{nm} = 10^{19} \text{ m}^{-2}$ (in the transverse direction) and then it falls deep into the graphite crystal. When the $R(I)$ layer is formed, internal stress-strain states arise in it. It has been shown that it is much easier to destroy graphite in the transverse direction ($\sigma_{Bc} \approx 40$ MPa), but in the longitudinal direction ($\sigma_{Ba} \approx 200$ MPa). The formulas proposed in the article make it possible to theoretically determine the critical length of cracks and the strength of not only graphite, but also carbon-carbon composite materials.

Keywords: graphite, surface layer thickness, crack length, strength, crystal, metal, density, carbon, composite.

Introduction

An alternative definition of strength is formulated in [1] and looks like this: strength is the property of a material to resist the occurrence of cracks in it during deformation. From here it becomes clear that the deformation of a material without the occurrence of cracks is one of the types of flow (viscous, plastic, etc.). The strength of graphite varies significantly depending on the method of its manufacture, therefore graphites with the same density, but of different grades, differing in structure, can have different strengths [2]. The general rule is that a finer structured graphite composite tends to have greater strength. Graphite is a thermodynamically

stable allotropic modification of carbon - an element of the 4th group of the main subgroup of the 2nd period of the periodic system, serial number 6, atomic mass of a natural mixture of isotopes 12.0107 g/mol [3]. The theoretical density of 2.26 g/cm³ is achieved only in natural graphite. The density of artificial graphite is in the range of 1.65-1.75 g/cm³ [4]. Such a low density of artificial graphite is explained by its porosity. Graphite does not melt, but sublimates at a temperature of about 3650 °C [5]. The crystal structure of graphite has hexagonal symmetry and consists of flat layers of carbon atoms located parallel to each other (Fig. 1a). The phase diagram of carbon according to Bundy [6] is shown in Fig. 1b.

Figure 1. Structure of α -graphite (a) and phase diagram of carbon (b).

In α -graphite, half of the atoms of each layer are located above and below the centers of the hexagon (laying...AVAVA VA...) (see Fig. 1a). Each carbon atom is covalently bonded to three other carbon atoms surrounding it. Since the bonds acting in the basal planes (bond energy is 420...460 kJ/mol) and the bonds between these basal planes (bond energy is 42 kJ/mol) are very different, there is a strong anisotropy of properties in single-crystalline graphite, and this determines the features properties and structure of polycrystalline graphites.

Very important factors to consider when modeling a graphite block in a nuclear reactor are the initiation and growth of cracks. It is these processes that lead to the accumulation of stresses and strains in graphite [7, 8].

In this work, we will demonstrate our work [9] on

determining the length of nanocracks and apply it to graphite.

Surface layer thickness and length of nanocracks in graphite

The thickness of the surface layer $R(I)$ and the length of nanocracks L_{nm} are given by the empirical formula [10, 11]:

$$R(I) = L_{nm} = 0,17 \cdot 10^{-9} \cdot \alpha \cdot \nu \text{ [m]}. \quad (1)$$

In equation (1), you need to know one parameter - the molar volume of the element, which is equal to $\nu = M/\rho$ (M is the molar mass, ρ is its density), $\alpha = 1 \text{ m}^{-2}$ - a constant, so that the dimension ($R(I) = \text{[m]}$). Using formula (1), we calculate $R(I) = L_{nm}$ (Table 1) for graphite parallel to the plane $x = a = b$ and perpendicular to this plane $x = c$.

Table 1.

Parameters $R(I) = L_{nm}$ of graphite.

Graphite	Structure	M, g/mol	ρ , g/sm ³	$R(I)_a = L_{nma}$, nm	$R(I)_c = L_{nmc}$, nm
C	C6/mmc-D ⁴ _{6h}	12,0107	2,26	0.90 (3)	2.46 (3)
			1,75	1.17 (4)	3.19 (4)
			1,65	1.24 (5)	3.39 (5)

From the table Figure 1 shows that the thickness of the layer $R(I)_a$ (and the length of nanocracks L_{nma}) varies from 0.9 to 1.24 nm in the upper plane (Fig. 1a), and the thickness of the layer $R(I)_c$ (and the length of nanocracks L_{nmc}) varies from 2.46 to 3.39 nm perpendicular to this plane (Fig. 1a). This is due to changes in the density of graphite and its layered structure. Table

2 shows the thickness of the surface layer of some cubic metals, which is also a nanostructure with a size of about 2 nm. In table 1 and 2, the number in brackets represents the number of layers - $n = R(I)/a$ (a is the crystal lattice constant of the metal). It can be seen that the number of metal layers in graphite is 3-5.

Table 2.

Elastic parameters of some hard metals

Metal	$R(I)$, nm	W_a , J/m ²	ϵ_{is} , GPa	E , GPa
Au	1.73 (4)	1.337	7.813	79
Ag	1.75 (4)	1.235	7.665	83
Cu	1.21 (3)	1.357	12.000	110
Mn	1.30 (2)	1.517	15.199	198
Ni	1.12 (3)	1.726	17.776	207
Fe	1.21 (4)	1.812	17.550	211
Cr	1.23 (4)	2.130	21.977	279
Mo	1.60 (5)	2.896	24.413	293
W	1.62 (5)	3.695	30.611	371

Other parameters are in the table. 2 will be discussed later. Now we will say the most important thing. We will call the layer $R(I)$ the surface layer and denote the surface energy of this layer by γ_1 . In general, there are two approaches: the Gibbs approach [13], in which the surface layer is conventionally considered as a geometric surface without thickness; the approach of Van der Wals, Guggenheim, Rusanov, in which the surface layer is considered as a layer of finite thickness [14]. According to modern concepts [15, 16], the surface phase γ_1 is understood as an ultrathin film (surface

layer) that is in equilibrium with a crystalline base (substrate), the properties and structure of which are different from the bulk properties of γ_2 . However, the question of the theoretical "thickness" of this surface layer for various substances remained open until 2018. Only after our works [10, 11] it became clear how the thickness of the surface layer, which plays a big role in nanotechnology and mesomechanics, can be theoretically determined [17].

In the surface layer $R(I)$, relaxation or reconstruction [15] of atomic monolayers occurs (Fig. 2).

Figure 2. – Transformation of the metal surface

Size effects in the R(I) layer are determined by the entire collective of atoms in the system (collective processes). Such “quasi-classical” size effects are observed only in nanoparticles and nanostructures [18]. Experimentally, R(I) can be observed on very pure single crystals in high vacuum with grazing incidence of X-ray radiation, when the angle of incidence is equal to or less than the critical angle of total internal reflection [15]. When the angle of incidence becomes less than the critical one, the refracted wave decays exponentially in the volume at a characteristic depth of the order of several nanometers (for example, for silicon this depth is $R(I) = 3.2$ nm, and for gold $R(I) = 1.2$ nm) [15].

In [12] it is shown that the surface energy of a bulk metal γ_2 , with an accuracy of 3%, is equal to:

$$\gamma_2 = 0,7 \cdot 10^{-3} \cdot T_m \text{ [J/m}^2\text{]}, \quad (2)$$

where T_m is the melting temperature of the metal (K).

In the R(I) layer, it is necessary to take into account the size effect and the surface energy of the R(I) layer becomes equal to γ_1 [9]:

$$\gamma_1 = \gamma_2(1 - R(I)/R(I) + h) \approx 0,3\gamma_2, \quad (3)$$

Equation (3) shows that the surface energy of the R(I) layer is three times less than the surface energy of the main crystal. To separate the R(I) layer from the rest of the crystal, it is necessary to expend energy, which is called adhesion energy [19]:

$$W_a = \gamma_1 + \gamma_2 - \gamma_{12} \approx \gamma_1 + \gamma_2 = 1,3\gamma_2, \quad (4)$$

where γ_{12} is the surface energy at the phase interface, which is negligible due to a second-order phase transition.

Internal voltages σ_{is} between phases γ_1 and γ_2 can be calculated using the formula [19]:

$$\sigma_{is} = \sqrt{W_a \cdot \dot{A}/R(I)}, \quad (5)$$

where E is Young's modulus of elasticity.

Using equations (1) – (5), we calculate the elastic parameters for graphite.

Table 3.

Elastic parameters of graphite						
Graphite	W_{aa} , J/m ²	W_{ac} , J/m ²	σ_{isa} , MPa	σ_{isc} , MPa	E_a , GPa	E_c , GPa
C ($\rho = 2,26$)	3,613	1,323	5740	1370	7,59	3,48
C ($\rho = 1,75$)	2,801	1,026	3750	930	5,88	2,70
C ($\rho = 1,65$)	2,637	0,966	3440	870	5,55	2,55

For graphite, the average value is $T_m = 3970$ K and $\gamma_2 = 2.779$ J/m² (see formula (2)). According to work [2], graphite with a density $\rho = 1.75$ g/cm³ refers to pressed samples, and with a density $\rho = 1.65$ g/cm³ refers to pressed samples. Because of this, their mechanical properties differ both in the longitudinal (for example, Young's modulus $E = E_a$) and in the transverse directions ($E = E_c$) (Table 3). The Young's modulus of graphite is 10 ÷ 100 times less than that of most metals (Table 2). However, the magnitude of internal stresses is 2 times less than that of gold and silver.

Defects and cracks in graphite.

Defects in graphite, according to [2, 20, 21], can be divided into two types: defects related to disturbances between layers and bond defects in networks. The first include layer packing defects, characterized by a

violation of the packing order of parallel layers of hexagonal networks. Thus, carbon consisting of fairly perfect hexagonal networks, but with a disturbed order in the sequence of layer packing, is usually called turbostratic. In such a structure, graphite-like networks are randomly displaced relative to each other (with a random vector of displacement of one layer relative to another).

The second type of structural damage in graphite is defects in the bonds of the carbon lattice. These include vacancies and their groups, impurity atoms embedded in the hexagonal layer, defects in isomeric bonds when some of the atoms have sp³ hybridization, edge defects, screw dislocations, etc.

Cracks in solids (and graphite) occur mainly for three reasons. Firstly, the root cause of crack formation

is stresses associated with the formation of a surface nanostructured layer due to relaxation processes or surface reconstruction [9]. They are called natural (or primary) cracks or nanocracks (see Table 1 - Lnm), which were experimentally discovered quite recently in minerals by fractoluminescence [22]. Secondly, cracks arise due to the process of crystal growth from a melt, from a solution or from a gas phase with changes in temperature, pressure, impurities, etc. They are called technological cracks. Thirdly, cracks can occur when a solid body (especially metals) interacts with the external environment. They are called corrosion cracks.

The numerical value of these nanocracks is determined by equation (1) and is presented in table. 2. The

$$V_{max} = \frac{dL}{dt} = \sqrt{\frac{1-\nu}{4(1+\nu)[\nu^2 - 3\nu\nu/ + 7/8] \ln 5,2 - 3\nu\nu/ + 3/32}} \cdot \sqrt{\frac{E}{\rho}},$$

$$\text{at } \nu = 0,25 \quad V_{max} = 0,38 \cdot \sqrt{\frac{E}{\rho}}. \tag{7}$$

In equation (7), the speed $V_0 \approx \sqrt{E/\rho}$ is equal to the speed of sound in the volume, which means that the Griffiths formula for the limiting speed of crack propagation is also valid. However, calculating this speed using formula (6) is much more difficult (β, γ_1, W_a) than

maximum speed of crack propagation according to Griffiths theory is equal to [23]:

$$V_C = \beta \cdot V_0 \cdot (1 - \gamma_1 / W_a)^{1/2} \tag{6}$$

and is about 1/3 of the speed of sound V_0 in the material.

After Griffiths, a significant number of works were published in which various models of crack development were analyzed, but we make a choice in work [24], where it became possible to calculate the maximum crack propagation speed V_{max} in solid materials for which the main mechanical characteristics are known (E – Young's modulus, ν - Poisson's ratio, ρ - material density):

$$V_{max} = \frac{dL}{dt} = \sqrt{\frac{1-\nu}{4(1+\nu)[\nu^2 - 3\nu\nu/ + 7/8] \ln 5,2 - 3\nu\nu/ + 3/32}} \cdot \sqrt{\frac{E}{\rho}},$$

$$\text{at } \nu = 0,25 \quad V_{max} = 0,38 \cdot \sqrt{\frac{E}{\rho}}. \tag{8}$$

using formula (7) - (E, ρ, ν).

If we substitute the formula for $R(I)$ into the last formula (7), then we have:

Integrating both sides of formula (8) and squaring them, we have:

$$L_{max} = 0.07 \cdot \frac{E \cdot R_0 \cdot T}{\gamma M} \cdot t^2. \tag{9}$$

According to formula (9), the length of a nanocrack depends quadratically on the time of applied voltage E and depends linearly on temperature T .

In [25], some metals were subjected to stresses from 5 to 70 GPa, which led to a change in $\Delta\rho/\rho$ and the movement of nanocracks according to equations (6) and (7). As a result, the resulting microcracks were ex-

amined by L_R X-ray and L_V electron microscopy methods. Their results are shown in table. 4.

From the table 4 it follows that within the experimental errors: $L_{\mu m} = 10^2 L_{nm}$.

$$L_{\mu m} = 10^2 \cdot L_{nm} \tag{10}$$

According to work [26], the critical length of cracks L_C of most metals and alloys lies in the range of 30-50 μm , which is much greater than $L_{\mu m} \approx 0.2 \mu m$.

This leads to the conclusion that the critical length of cracks in metals must be determined taking into account formulas (6) and (8), and a similar formula (10) (Table 4):

$$L_C = 10^4 \cdot L_{nm} = 0.17 \cdot 10^{-5} \cdot \nu = 0.17 \cdot 10^{-5} \cdot M / \rho \tag{11}$$

Table 4.

Length of cracks in metals

Metal	L_{nm} , nm	$L_{\mu m}$, nm	L_R , nm [25]	L_V , nm [25]	L_C , nm
Fe	1.21	121	90	100	12100
Al	1.70	170	140	200	17000
Ni	1.12	112	80	100	11200
Cu	1.21	121	-	250	12100
Ag	1.75	175	-	200	17500
Au	1.73	173	-	200	17300
Mo	1.60	160	-	80	16000

If for iron as L_C we take the values of L_{nm} from the table. 2, i.e. $L_C = 1.21 \cdot 10^{-5} \text{ m} = 12.1 \text{ }\mu\text{m}$, then for the strength of iron [26]: $(K_{Ic})^2 = 2\gamma E/(1-\mu^2) = 65.5 \cdot 10^{10}$; $(\sigma_B)^2 = (K_{Ic})^2/L_C = 541.3 \cdot 10^{14}$; $\sigma_B = 233 \text{ MPa}$. In the reference book – $\sigma_B = 250 \text{ MPa}$, which is consistent with

the nanocrack growth model: $L_{nm} \rightarrow 10^2 L_{\mu m} \rightarrow 10^4 L_C$.

Let's calculate the crack length L_{nm} , $L_{\mu m}$, L_C for graphite.

Table 5.

Length of graphite cracks.

Graphite	L_{nma} , nm	L_{nmc} , nm	$L_{\mu ma}$, nm	$L_{\mu mc}$, nm	L_{Ca} , nm	L_{Cc} , nm
C	0.90	2.46	90	246	9000	24600
	1.17	3.19	117	319	11700	31900
	1.24	3.39	124	339	12400	33900

Cracks L_{nm} , $L_{\mu m}$, L_C for graphite are caused by their dislocation interaction [27]. The work [28] provides a review of modern methods for studying and calculating the dislocation density in single crystals. A brief analysis of the main advantages and disadvantages of each method is given, as well as experimental results. In Fig. 3 shows some results.

The dislocation structure of a crystal is usually characterized by the scalar dislocation density ρ [29]. Dislocation multiplication and dislocation reactions are random processes. Therefore, dislocations inhibited in this way are called statistically stored ρ_S (SSD) [29]. Statistically stored dislocations are inhibited by relatively weak barriers - other dislocations.

Figure 3. TEM micrographs of GaAs dislocations (a); synchrotron double-crystal transmission topogram of germanium reflection (111): visible scratch, dislocation, inclusion (b) [28].

In the case of relaxation of the R(I) layer, stress gradients arise, then in addition to the dislocation density ρ_S , the accumulation of geometrically necessary dislocations (GNDs) with a density ρ_G occurs [29].

In this case:

$$\rho = \rho_S + \rho_G \tag{12}$$

Taking into account equation (11), for the dislocation density we have:

$$\begin{aligned} \rho_{nm} &= (L_{nm} \cdot b)^{-1}, \\ \rho_{\mu m} &= (L_{\mu m} \cdot b)^{-1}, \\ \rho_{\tilde{N}} &= (L_{\tilde{N}} \cdot b)^{-1}. \end{aligned} \tag{13}$$

where b is the Burgers vector.

The dislocation density in graphite is shown in table 6. From the table 6 it can be seen that the dislocation density is maximum in the layer R(I) $\rho_{nma} = 10^{18} \text{ m}^{-2}$ (in the longitudinal direction), $\rho_{nmc} = 10^{19} \text{ m}^{-2}$ (in the transverse direction) and then it falls deep into the graphite crystal.

Table 6.

Graphite dislocation density

Graphite	$\rho_{nma}, 10^{18} \text{ m}^{-2}$	$\rho_{nmc}, 10^{19} \text{ m}^{-2}$	$\rho_{\mu ma}, 10^8 \text{ m}^{-2}$	$\rho_{\mu mc}, 10^9 \text{ m}^{-2}$	$\rho_{Ca}, 10^4 \text{ m}^{-2}$	$\rho_{Cc}, 10^5 \text{ m}^{-2}$
C	4,5	6,1	4,5	6,1	4,5	6,1
	3,5	4,7	3,5	4,7	3,5	4,7
	3,3	4,4	3,3	4,4	3,3	4,4

According to work [30], in an annealed single crystal the number of dislocations can be 10^8 - 10^{10} m^{-2} . At the same time, in an annealed polycrystal, ρ already reaches 10^{10} - 10^{12} m^{-2} , and in a highly deformed state up to 10^{16} m^{-2} (so that the average distance between adjacent dislocations becomes approximately 10 nm). Table 3 shows that highly deformed states σ_{is} arise in the

R(I) layer, so that the dislocation density is quite significant. Strongly deformed states σ_{is} lead to features in the structure of dislocations noted in [31]. As the authors of [31] believe, it's all about dislocations that arise where the graphene layers in graphite are rotated at a small angle relative to each other (Fig. 4).

Figure 4.

Schematic representation of the occurrence of dislocations at the boundaries of graphite granules [31].

In Fig. Figure 4 (left) shows the initial stacking of graphene layers forming a small angle θ_{twist} with each other (for simplicity, a square rather than a hexagonal lattice is shown in the graphene layers). In Fig. Figure 4 (right) shows a relaxed state with large areas of lattices coinciding with each other, separated by thin boundaries - screw dislocations, in which mechanical stress is concentrated and anomalies in the conductive properties of graphite are observed.

Instead of the usual superposition of two lattices (Fig. 4a), regions with atoms in layers that are ideally fitted to each other appear, separated by transition regions - dislocations, forming a large-scale network with a period from 3 to 25 nm (Fig. 4b). In places of dislocations, mechanical stresses lead to the formation of a flat energy zone and, as a consequence, a singularity in the density of energy states of electrons, which, in turn, gives rise to high-temperature superconductivity.

However, in [31], the described mechanism does not allow us to explain the features of the phenomenon:

due to its poor reproducibility, instability and weakness of the signal - after all, superconducting “corridors” occupy a small volume compared to the total thickness of graphite and their very existence is highly dependent on the preparation conditions: Even the smallest adsorption of foreign atoms (eg hydrogen) can destroy the fragile superconducting state.

Graphite Strength

When the R(I) layer is formed, internal stress-strain states σ_{is} (SSS) arise in it (Table 3). The R(I) layer is similar to a thin coating on a substrate (Fig. 5) [32]. In a coating, SDS creates an energetic state that prevents adhesion and promotes peeling of the coating. SSS energy can be estimated using the formula [33]:

$$W_{in} = (\sigma_{is}^2 / 2\text{\AA}) \cdot S \cdot R(I), \quad (14)$$

where $S = 1$ m^2 – coverage area, E – Young’s modulus.

Figure 5. Distribution of contact pressures and isolines of tensile-compressive stresses $\sigma_r(r,z)/p_n$ in the coating and in the substrate [32].

For example, let's calculate W_{in} ($\rho = 1.75$) using table 3: $W_{in} \approx 1.4 \text{ J/m}^2$; $W_{in} \approx 0.5 \text{ J/m}^2$. If we compare W_{in} with the adhesion energy W_a from the table. 3, it turns out that $W_{aa} > W_{in} \sim 2$ times; $W_{ac} > W_{bc} \sim 2$ times. In other words, the energy of internal stresses W_{in} is 2 times less than the adhesion energy W_a of graphite in both the longitudinal and transverse directions.

This means that internal stresses cannot tear off

$$\frac{K_{1N}^2(1-\mu^2)}{E} = 2\delta_{1N}\sigma_B = G_{1N} = J_{1N} = 2\gamma = W_a, \quad (15)$$

where K_{1c} is the critical stress intensity factor, the force criterion for destruction; E - elastic modulus; μ - Poisson's ratio; δ_{1c} - critical opening at the crack tip, deformation criterion of destruction; σ_B - tensile strength; G_{1c} - critical intensity of released energy, energy criterion of destruction; J_{1c} - critical j-integral, energy criterion of destruction; γ - surface energy, W_a - adhesion energy.

Wherein:

the R(I) layer and it is a stable structure that is in equilibrium with the crystalline base (substrate), the properties and structure of which are different from the bulk properties.

For the destruction of a solid body, force, deformation and energy failure criteria have been developed. There is the following connection between them [26]:

$$K_{1N} = \sqrt{EJ_{1N}}. \quad (16)$$

In the case of a plate with a crack L_C :

$$\hat{E}_{1N} = \sigma_{is} \sqrt{L_N}, \quad \delta_{1N} = K_{1N}^2 / \sigma_{is} \cdot E. \quad (17)$$

Let us evaluate equations (15), (16) and (17) for graphite (Table 7).

Table 7.

Graphite failure criteria

Graphite	K_{1Ca} , GPa m ^{1/2}	K_{1Cc} , GPa m ^{1/2}	δ_{1Ca} , nm	δ_{1Cc} , nm	σ_{Ba} , MPa	σ_{Bc} , MPa
C	545300	215090	6,1	9,7	296	68
	397500	166470	7,2	11,0	194	47
	381840	160080	7,6	11,6	173	42

From the table 7 it is clear that it is much easier to destroy graphite in the transverse direction, while in the longitudinal direction. This is illustrated in Table. 8,

which shows various carbon-carbon composite materials.

Table 8.

Strength of carbon-carbon composite materials

Composite	SG-P	SG-M	MPG-7	MIG-2	NIIGrafit
Density g/cm ³	2.2	2.1	1.8	1.8	1.45
Tensile strength longitudinal, MPa	420	125	103	80	130
Tensile strength transverse, MPa	100	65	49	30	60

Listed in table 8 carbon-carbon composite materials are used as components of friction units (o-rings, heels, plain bearings, etc.) in pumps, reactors, separators and other equipment; for protective fittings of immersion thermocouples, for stop-pouring supplies of metallurgical furnaces and ladles, etc. Artificial graphites of the MPG-7 and MIG-2 grades are high-strength thermally resistant materials based on a special coke-pitch composition.

Conclusion

The formula $L_C = 0.17 \cdot 10^{-3} M/\rho$ proposed in equation (11) allows one to theoretically determine the critical crack length and strength not only of graphite, but also of carbon-carbon composite materials, the synthesis of which is important for use in nuclear engineering, aviation, metallurgy, space technology and other industries.

References

- Litvinsky G.G. Analytical theory of strength of rocks and massifs. - Donetsk: Nord-Press, 2008. - 207 p.
- Zhmurikov E.I., Bubnenkov I.A., Dremov V.V., Samarin S.I., Pokrovsky A.S., Kharkov D.V. Graphite in science and nuclear technology. - Novosibirsk, 2013. - 193 p.
- Knunyants I.L. (chief ed.). Chemical encyclopedia: 5 volumes - M.: Sov. enz. 1988. V.1. - 623 p.
- Asinovsky E.I., Kirillin A.V., Kostanovsky A.V. Experimental study of the properties of carbon at high temperatures and moderate pressures // UFN, 2002, V 172, No. 8. - P. 932-944.
- Savvatimsky A.I. Melting of graphite and liquid carbon // UFN, 2003, V. 173, No. 12. - P. 1371-1379.
- Bundy F.P., Bassett W.A., Weathers M.S., et al. The Pressure-Temperature Phase and Transformation Diagram for Carbon; Updated Through 1994 // Carbon, 1996, V. 34, N 2. - P. 141-153.
- Panyukov S.V., Subbotin A.V., Arzhakov M.V. Irradiation induced dimensional changes in bulk graphite: The theory. // Journal of Nuclear Materials, 2013, V. 439. - P. 72-83.
- Alekseev A.T. Modeling of thermomechanical behavior of the graphite block of the RBMK-1000 reactor using advanced calculation algorithms. - Dissertation of Technical Sciences, Moscow, 2017. - 133 p.
- Yurov V.M., Goncharenko V.I., Oleshko V.S. Study of primary nanocracks in atomically smooth metals // Letters to ZhTP, 2023, V. 49, No. 8. - P. 35-38.
- Yurov V.M. Thickness of the surface layer of atomically smooth crystals // Physical and chemical aspects of studying clusters, nanostructures and nanomaterials, 2019, No. 11. - P. 389-397.
- Yurov V.M., Goncharenko V.I., Oleshko V.S., Sha Mingun. Anisotropy of the surface of carbon materials // Eurasian Physical Technical Journal, 2021, Vol. 18, No. 3(37). - P. 15-24.
- Rekhviashvili S.Sh., Kishtikova E.V., Karmokova R.Yu. On the calculation of the Tolman constant // Letters to ZhTP, 2007, V. 33, Issue. 2. - P. 1-7.
- Gibbs J.W. Thermodynamic works. - M.: GITTL, 1950. - 303 p.
- Rusanov A.I. Phase equilibria and surface phenomena. - L.: Chemistry, 1967. - 346 p.
- Oura K., Lifshits V.G., Saranin A.A. etc. Introduction to surface physics. - M.: Nauka, 2006. - 490p.
- Roldugin V.I. Physical chemistry of the surface. Dolgoprudny: Publishing House "Intelligence", 2008. - 568 p.
- Panin V.E., Sergeev V.P., Panin A.V. Nanostructuring of surface layers of structural materials and application of nanostructured coatings // Tomsk: TPU Publishing House, 2010. - 254 p.
- Uvarov N.F., Boldyrev V.V. Size effects in the chemistry of heterogeneous systems // Uspekhi khimii, 2001, V. 70 (4). - P. 307-329.
- Zimon A.D. Adhesion of films and coatings. - M.: Chemistry, 1977. - 352 p.
- Ubellode A.R., Lewis F.A. Graphite and its crystalline compounds. - M.: Mir, 1965. - 256 p.
- Kostikov V.I., Shipkov N.N., Kalashnikov Ya.A. and others. Graphitization and diamond formation. - M.: Metallurgy, 1991. - 223 p.
- Vettegren V.I., Ponomarev A.V., Mamalimov R.I., Shcherbakov I.P. Nanocracks during the destruction of oligoclase // Physics of the Earth, 2021, No. 6. - P. 87-92.
- Griffith A.A. The phenomena of rupture and flow in solids // Philos. Trans. Roy. Soc. London. Ser. A., 1920, V. 221. - P. 163-198.
- Chekunaev N.I., Kaplan A.M. Limiting speed of crack propagation in elastic materials // Applied mechanics and technical physics, 2009, V. 50, No. 4. - P. 158-166.
- Betekhtin V.I., Kadomtsev A.G. Evolution of microscopic cracks and pores in loaded solids // FTT, 2005, vol. 47, issue. 5. - P. 801-807.
- Erasov V.S., Oreshko E.I. Reasons for the dependence of the mechanical characteristics of the crack resistance of a material on the size of the sample // Aviation materials and technologies, 2018, No. 3(52). - P. 56-64.
- Karkina L.E., Yakovenkova L.I. Initiation of microcracks during dislocation interactions in single-crystal Ti_3Al // FTT, 2008, vol. 50, No. 6. - P. 1018-1027.
- Knyazev S.N., Kudrya A.V., Komarovskiy N.Yu., Parkhomenko Yu.N., Molodtsova E.V., Yushchuk V.V. Methods for studying the dislocation structure of semiconductor single crystals of group AIIIBV // Izvestia VUZov. Materials of electronic technology, 2022, V. 25, No. 4. - P. 323-336.
- Kozlov E.V., Popova N.A., Koneva N.A. Size effect in dislocation substructures of metallic materials // Fundamental problems of modern materials science, 2009, Vol. 6, No. 2. - P. 14-24.
- Baraz V.R., Levchenko V.P., Povzner A.A. Structure and physical properties of crystals. - Ekaterinburg: USTU-UPI, 2009. - 164 p.
- Esquinazi P., Heikkilä T.T., Lysogorskiy Y.V., Tayurskii D.A., Volovik G.E. On the superconductivity of graphite interfaces // Pis'ma v ZhETF, vol. 100, iss. 5. - P. 374-378.
- Torskaya E.V. Modeling of frictional interaction of bodies with coatings. - Dissertation of Doctor of Physics and Mathematics. Sciences, Moscow, 2014. - 251p.
- Ainbinder S.B., Panch A.S. The influence of the relative mechanical properties of metals on the formation and destruction of adhesion at low sliding speeds. - In the book: Dry friction. Riga, 1961. - P. 64-79.